

Citizen Science Based Methodology for FL and FW Reduction and Prevention

D2.3

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Summary

The FOODRUS project will test 23 circular solutions to limit food loss and waste across three food value chains: vegetables and prepared salads (Spain); meat and fish (Denmark); and bread (Slovakia).

The solutions will empower and engage all the agents of the local food systems, creating a sense of community and building a multi-actor alliance to tackle the challenge of food loss and waste. FOODRUS will also empower citizens to become an active part of the solution.

To promote the replicability of the tested solutions FOODRUS will prepare best practice toolkits involving six European regions as Followers, to replicate and adapt the solutions in: Timisoara (Romania), Budapest (Hungary), Linz (Austria), Plovdiv (Bulgaria), Halandri (Greece), Arnhem-Nijmegen (Netherlands), Amsterdam (Netherlands) and Catalunya (Spain).

The purpose of this document is to collect the Citizen Science based methodology for food loss (FL) and food waste (FW) reduction and prevention to be applied in the project. Moreover, this document also describes some of the actions of the FOODRUS' social programme, which includes 4 main strategies (Food donation awareness campaign, Healthy and Sustainable diets promotion, Zero waste – revalorization, Zero waste – reduction/prevention) and the citizen science activities (CS) to be developed in the different pilots, which will be further detailed in the present document. The general aim of the Social Program and the CS is promoting a participatory process and a citizens co-governance model.

The different CS have been classified and developed with slight adaptations to each pilot's needs. Information of reference on the schedule, methodology, objectives and participation of different citizens and stakeholders is provided in this document. This document has been developed to show the planification of the CSs, although their deployment and results will be described in D1.4 (Full test report, due in M40).

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1. INTRODUCTION

Citizen science (CS) is defined as scientific work undertaken by members of the general public, often in collaboration with, or under, the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions. Production of scientific knowledge implies that participants are involved in the material and cognitive process of scientific research and enquiry.

Including CS activities in research projects is suitable especially in some cases. For example, when data needs to be collected across large geographical areas or during a long period of time, CS can be more cost-effective than other methods. Moreover, when the research is intended to have a significant local or social impact, CS ensures that the research and the results are more locally relevant. Furthermore, CS activities allow to obtain information in a real-life context, providing data about contextual factors that may influence individual and collective behaviour (ECSA, n.d.; ETH Zurich, 2021). However, CS is also challenging and many of the issues relate to the variety and diversity of actors involved. Some of the challenges to be addressed in CS are: 1. Lack of awareness and stakeholder engagement, especially in long-term projects; 2. data collection and data quality; 2. the different interests and motivations of the stakeholders, 2. ethical issues, 3. the relations between researchers and participants; 4. lack of a common language, as terms can be used and adopted in different manners, 5. evaluating the outcomes (Burgess et al., 2017; Vohland et al., 2021).

In this sense, CS must be well designed and planned for a successful project's development (Vohland et al., 2021).

Projects involving citizen science can take many different forms, involving various levels of participant and project organizers collaboration. Depending on who drives the initiative, we distinguish between top-down initiatives driven by institutions or governing bodies, and bottom-up approaches driven by citizens or the public. On the other hand, attending to the level of collaboration among stakeholders, three main types of projects can be identified: 1. contributory projects are those designed by professional researchers, where citizens' role is mainly as data providers; 2. collaborative projects are also designed by professional researchers but citizens play a more relevant role participating in other activities, such as data analysis or communication activities; 3. co-created projects are those in which both professional researchers and the general public participate actively in the definition and all the stages of the project .

FOODRUS aims to have a significant social impact boosting best practices to reduce FL and FW in all the food value chain. In this sense in the FOODRUS project different contributory, collaborative and co-creative activities are developed following the "White paper on Citizen Science: citizen science for Europe" (Socientize Project, 2014).

The CS have been designed using different approaches and considering various target groups of citizens, depending on the specific aim of the activity, and on contextual factors of each of the pilots. In general, the dynamics of CS could be considered similar to other qualitative social/citizen research methods such as personal interviews, focus groups, or focus panels. In this project, the *living lab methodology* explained in detail in D2.1. is being implemented in the different CS to empower all agents of the specific agri-food value chains (meat & fish, salads, bread), and create inclusive food circular strategies.

The sum of the social activities deployed in each pilot, and which can be considered the different research living labs described in D2.1. (Denmark: 'corporate' located in university canteens; Spain: 'organizational styled' in Zamudio; Slovakia: 'organizational'), include the different CS. The CS can be classified according to the main methodologies and active members responsible for the deployment:

- CS1, CS3, CS8 and CS9 are those that actively involve diverse **citizen groups** to provide data, stories, recipes, opinions, etc. The interaction with citizens is different depending on the pilot (Spain, Denmark or Slovakia) and the specific activity (e.g.: women in CS3) yet most of them still being active participants.
- CS2, CS4, CS5, CS6, CS7 and CS10 are activities in which different stakeholders and experts interact in a series or **working groups** driven to identify potential solutions, barriers, methodologies, etc.

In the following sections the methodology for including CS in projects in a general manner will be described. Then, the explanation of the methodology for each one of the specific CS to be implemented in the FOODRUS project will be explained. Some examples from the three pilots will be provided to help other potential researchers in adopting the citizen science approach in their projects.

2. METHODOLOGY

Involving different stakeholders in research projects is always challenging, as usually they have different views, needs, interests and skills. However, their active participation in the projects is essential because it helps to ensure that the results produced are relevant to real-world issues. Moreover, it raises the awareness of those involved, as well as the impact and applicability of the project outcomes, because participants are not only adopters but also knowledge providers.

The FOODRUS project aims to reduce food waste and losses in the whole agri-food supply chain, which implies the involvement of a wide range of different stakeholders. In this sense, citizen science-based methodology can help to improve project impact as the final users also take part in the research process.

Citizen science approach implies the use of different research methods and tools, depending on the objective of the project, the type of data to be collected, the stakeholders involved, project duration and dedication or the location (ETH Zurich, 2021).

Figure 1 describes in a general manner the main steps of the methodology when using citizen science approaches.

Figure 1. Step by step methodology for citizen science activities (adapted from (ETH Zurich, 2021))

2.1. DESIGN

Another fundamental aspect of designing and planning the CS is the selection of the **research methods** to be applied. In this sense the selected research methods should meet the needs of the study.

The FOODRUS project adopted a co-creation approach from the beginning. Bearing this in mind, different working groups involving the project partners have been created at early stages of the project in order to co-create the solutions and discuss the methods to be applied.

Due to the COVID pandemic situation most of the working groups' meetings have been conducted online, and the dynamics could be assimilated as the one developed during the online focus groups or focus panels. The qualitative research methods aim at 1) obtaining relevant information from a group of individuals with a common interest, 2) discovering factors that motivate an individual to act in a particular way (for example, reasons to throw a product away or not), and/or 3) performing a systematic investigation of the basis of a subjective experience: beliefs, expectations, opinions, attitudes, and perceptions. Although different methods can be developed to reach these objectives, one of the most frequently chosen is focus groups (FGs): a type of qualitative research technique that uses an open discussion format, based on a series of questions, and whose objective is to obtain information about ideas and perceptions of a specific topic through the participants' communications. See table 1.

Table 1: Definition of Focus Groups (Guerrero & Xicola, 2018).

Schematic and Operational Definition of focus Groups					
People with -	specific characteristics -	that provide data -	of qualitative nature -	through a conversation -	guided by a moderator.
Usually between 7-10 people: small enough for everyone to have the opportunity to present their views and large enough for a good diversity of opinions.	Participants are fairly homogeneous; usually a group of members that do not know each other.	Data of interest for the research topic are produced; the purpose is not to reach consensus, develop proposals, or decide between alternatives.	The result is qualitative, providing information on attitudes, perceptions, and opinions; the data are obtained through open questions and the observation of participants, who influence one another.	The conversation of the group is guided from carefully selected and arranged topics; the open questions are prepared beforehand, and no pressure exists to achieve consensus.	Who listens, observes, and eventually analyses inductively testing hypotheses or theories a prior.

In general, the procedure for conducting FGs, independently of being online or face-to-face, is the following (Stewart et al., 2007):

1. Problem definition/formulation of the research question
 - What do we want to achieve?
 - What are we looking for with this research?
 - What information can be obtained from our group of participants?
 - What information is essential to meet the needs of the study?
2. Identification of sampling frame
 - n = 3 – 12 people
 - Heterogeneous/homogeneous group
 - How many FGs? Up to detecting redundant information.
 - Length of the sessions: 1-2 h
3. Choosing the moderator
4. Generation and pretesting of interview schedule

5. Recruiting the sample
6. Conducting the group
7. Analysis and data interpretation
8. Writing the report

During the different CS working groups (WG), the moderator/responsible of leading the WG, followed some adaptation of this methodology, encouraging participants to present their ideas and share standpoints, in order to use the information in later stages of the project.

Finally, a stakeholder mapping must be done, to identify the types and quantity of stakeholders needed for the study. In this sense a broad variety of stakeholders can participate in the CS by adopting different roles. According to (Göbel & Martin, 2017) stakeholders participating in CS projects could be categorized in six main groups: 1. Civil society organizations, informal groups and community members; 2. Academic and research organizations; 3. Government agencies and departments; 4. Participants (meaning volunteers or collaborators); 5. Formal learning institutions such as schools; and 6. Businesses or industry.

The FOODRUS consortium is formed by 27 partners from 10 different European countries. In the consortium itself, most of the identified stakeholder groups are represented: universities and research institutions, companies, business associations, municipalities, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). In addition, other stakeholders participate in the project contributing to knowledge generation throughout the CS, as shown in figure 2. In this sense, for each CS and for each pilot a stakeholder mapping should be done, taking into account the objectives, the needs and the context of each pilot.

Figure 2. Stakeholder mapping in FOODRUS project (source www.foodrus.eu)

The stakeholder map of the project is further explained in deliverable D1.1.

2.2. STAKEHOLDER'S RECRUITMENT

Once the stakeholder groups participating in the CS have been identified, appropriate recruitment strategies must be carried out to reach the number of participants needed for the research. In this sense, different target groups may require different recruitment strategies. Moreover, other local or contextual factors such as cultural or technological issues must be also taken into account.

In the FOODRUS project pilot leaders must decide which are the most suitable recruitment channels for their target audience: Zamudio citizens in the case of Spain; canteen users in the case of Denmark and families in the case of Slovakia.

2.3. STAKEHOLDER'S TRAINING

Citizen Science projects involve many agents in the generation of knowledge: researchers, professionals, and the general public, including citizens. This implies the adoption of methodologies or the use of certain protocols and tools with which some of the participants may not be familiar. Moreover, it may happen that the researchers and project partners themselves are not familiar with citizen science. In this sense, for a successful development of the project it is necessary to provide all the participants with all the information and tools they need to be able to complete their tasks in the project. This can include training on scientific procedures, technical issues such as the use of a specific tool for collecting or reporting data, ethical issues or another kind of dynamics or research methods. Moreover, the training also contributes to increasing stakeholders' awareness on the research (Socientize Project, 2014; Vohland et al., 2021).

The perceived quality of CS data is a significant issue in the scientific community and is frequently brought up as a barrier to the methodology's adoption. However, it has been demonstrated that if used correctly, citizens' contributions can meet the standards of professional scientists (Burgess et al., 2017; ETH Zurich, 2021). In this sense, this stage is crucial for ensuring the quality of the data required for successful research outcomes.

In the context of the project two training sessions led by BCC were conducted to train the rest of the project partners on how to perform CS. The two sessions took place online on May 21 and July 7, 2021.

In the same vein, pilot leaders have performed training sessions with their local stakeholders. For example, Zamudio citizens received training on how to measure their food waste and how to use the *Appfood*, developed by the University of Deusto, for reporting their data.

2.4. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Data collection in CS is challenging since data can come from a variety of sources and respond to different research objectives. In this sense, the choice of the appropriate methods and tools is very important. Projects including CS must foresee the tools they need from the beginning of the project. For example, technological tools, such as digital platforms or phone apps, to facilitate project participants in providing the data.

In the FOODRUS project, a combination of methods and tools are adapted to the needs of each CS and each pilot. In this sense, technological and non-technological means are used for data collection from the

stakeholders. For instance, a set of on-line surveys¹ are available at the project's web page targeting different stakeholder's groups, namely waste generators, waste managers, empowerment actors and sustainability actors. Other means used to collect the information from the living labs workshops with stakeholders are working groups, the Foodop app in the case of the Danish pilot, a web page to collect recipes and diaries to collect information on consumer habits and food waste generation, in the case of the Slovak pilot or the Appfood used in the case of the Spanish pilot to collect the information regarding food waste of households in the municipality of Zamudio. The pilot leaders report all activities relating to the CS deployment in their pilot through the Social Action Module (SAM²). Figure 3 shows the main screen of the SAM.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the SAM (source www.foodrus.eu)

2.5. MONITORING

To monitor the progress of CS, a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are suggested for each CS. The KPIs proposed in this document must be distinguished from the project's overall KPIs, that are described in D1.1. While the project's KPIs aim to monitor the overall progress of the project, the KPIs proposed in this document are meant to monitor the Living Labs (LLs)' progress. Moreover, it should be noted that the KPIs are specific to each CS activity at each pilot and may not be comparable among them because of the specificities of the activity and the pilot. In this sense, the proposed KPIs aim to evaluate the progress of CS in the LLs context in terms of stakeholder engagement and increasing awareness. The activities foreseen in this document will be implemented in work package 1 (WP1), therefore the deployment of CS will be further explained in D1.1.

The proposed methodology can be summarized in the following template, table 2. The template can help in the design and implementation of the CS.

¹ <https://www.foodrus.eu/stakeholders-map/>

² <https://social-actions.apps.foodrus.eu/>

Table 2: Proposed template for designing and implementing CS.

CS DESCRIPTION	
1	<p>SET THE OBJECTIVE (Set the objectives for the Citizen Science activity)</p> <p><i>For example: Monitoring waste generation at university canteens, including canteen users, to collect data for identifying the reasons for waste generation and potentially reducing canteen food waste by 50%.</i></p>
2	<p>STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING (Identify the stakeholders to be involved in the CS and define their role)</p> <p><i>For example:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pilot leaders and other pilot participants: recruitment of citizens. - Citizens/students/families/HORECA employees: data recording on food waste generation and reasons/associated behaviour. - Researchers of FOODRUS (e. g: data analyses, interaction with citizens, etc.)
3	<p>RECRUITMENT ACTIVITIES (Recruit the stakeholders to participate in the activity using the most appropriate channels according to the target groups)</p> <p><i>For example: social media campaigns; flyers, advertisements, etc.</i></p>
4	<p>TRAINING/INFORMATION ACTIVITIES (Provide the stakeholders with the information and training on the objectives, methods, and tools for an effective data collection)</p> <p><i>For example, on the use of the App where they report data, or regarding the survey; or new skills that allow them to implement actions, etc.</i></p>
5	<p>ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES/ RAISING AWARENESS ACTIVITIES (Develop activities to maintain stakeholder's interest and engagement throughout the project)</p> <p><i>For example: Social media content, Festivals, Cooking shows, etc.</i></p>
6	<p>DATA COLLECTION METHODS (Define and select the most appropriate methods to collect data taking into account the objective of the research and the stakeholders involved)</p> <p><i>For example: Surveys, APPs, Workshops results ...</i></p>
7	<p>KPIs (CS) (Define a set of indicators to monitor the progress of the CS and its impact)</p>
8	<p>MAIN RESULTS (Analyse the process and describe the main results of the CS, including best practices and barriers)</p>

3. CITIZEN SCIENCE ACTIVITIES

The following sections describe in detail the 10 CS of FOODRUS project. Each section has been structured following the proposed scheme. In this sense the main objectives and expected results, stakeholders and their roles, recruitment and training activities, methodologies to be applied, as well as the suggested KPIs for CS each pilot will be described.

3.1. CS1. Citizen groups to be monitored to identify shopping, cooking and waste generation habits and quality assessment of the main causes of FW.

In this section the methodology for the CS1 is explained. The implementation of CS1 in the FOODRUS project will be described in depth in D1.4.

3.1.1. Objective

The main objective of this activity is to identify the main causes of FW generation by the end-user in different environments, and to promote its reduction at different levels, involving citizens throughout the entire analysis process.

This activity will support each pilot to obtain data to reach the project objective of finding potential solutions for reducing FW. Moreover, CS aims to increase stakeholder engagement and can help to identify potential issues, such as barriers and good practices that may arise while putting solutions into practice and communicating them. The objective is not to decrease a great amount of waste within the pilot deployment, but to explore if end-users could have a significant role and if specific activities may encourage them to reduce food waste generation.

This activity is implemented by all pilots of the project. Each pilot develops in a unique environment with distinct goals, so the CSs must be adapted to fit the realities of each pilot.

CS1 objectives for each pilot are as follows:

- **Spanish pilot:** monitoring general waste at a municipal level, including citizens to collect qualitative information on the main reasons of generating ready-to-eat salads waste (to reduce it to a 50%), and to finally implement a PAYT system. In the Spanish pilot CS1 will concentrate in the municipality of Zamudio.
- **Danish pilot:** monitoring waste generation at university canteens, including canteen users, to collect data for identifying the reasons for waste generation and potentially reducing canteen food waste 50%. In the Danish pilot CS1 will focus on the University canteen.
- **Slovak pilot:** identifying behavioural causes to bread waste generation at the household level and contributing to changing their habits and improving their overall food waste behaviour in order to stop or reduce bread and bakery waste by 50%. Households will learn how to store and use up bread. The additional goal is to reduce bread packaging by 30%. In the Slovak pilot CS1 will focus on several households.

3.1.2. Expected result.

With the deployment of the CS1 in the three pilots a better understanding of the main reasons and potential corrections of food waste at a citizen level is expected. This result will be obtained by identifying the proportion of waste generated during a specific period, and the motivations or behaviours associated with waste generation. In addition, potential interventions could be investigated, as well as the effect of a social awareness campaign to decrease food waste generation.

3.1.3. Stakeholder mapping - Participants in the development of the CS1

For a successful implementation of CS1 the involvement of a diversity of stakeholders with different roles is needed. Moreover, because of the different characteristics and objectives, the type of stakeholders may differ from one pilot to another. Table 3 shows the stakeholders for CS1.

Table 3: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS1 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SPANISH PILOT	DANISH PILOT	SLOVAK PILOT	ROLE
Pilot Leaders	Municipality of Zamudio	University of Copenhagen	Slovak University of Agriculture	Recruitment of participants. Training activities. Engagement activities. Data collection. Monitoring.
Researchers of FOODRUS	University of Deusto. BCC.	University of Copenhagen BCC Jespers Torvekøkken	Slovak University of Agriculture BCC	Recruitment of participants. Methodology. Data analysis. Interaction with citizens (training activities, monitoring).
Other participants	Families	Canteen users	Families	Data providers (data recording on food waste generation and reasons/associated behaviour)

3.1.4. Methodology

In this section, the methodology to carry out the CS1 is described in a general manner.

To help citizens collect information about their food waste and consumption habits, and to standardize data collection within pilots, an App is being developed. The App developed by Deusto University, called *Appfood*, includes different checklists for citizens to mark the amount and kind of waste, reasons for throwing it away, etc. Slight adaptations are being included in the App to properly collect data in each pilot. The App is based on the Food Loss and Waste Calculator: [FLW Value Calculator - Food Loss and Waste Protocol \(flwprotocol.org\)](http://flwprotocol.org).

The adaptation of the methodology to the specificities of each pilot is described below. More detailed information about the App can be found in the deliverable D3.4.

SPANISH PILOT – Ready-to-eat salads.

In the case of the Spanish pilot, the target group to participate in this activity are the **citizens of Zamudio**.

To identify the purchasing, cooking, and waste generation habits of citizens of Zamudio, 10 families will be recruited to monitor their ready-to-eat salads consumption and associated habits. Moreover, the families will receive information about certain solutions for reducing food waste, and they will be monitored before and after that training.

The families chosen should be representative of the variety of family typologies in the municipality, which must be considered during the selection process. The expected monitoring period of the families will be 5 months, from November 2022 to March 2023. It is important to develop additional activities that contribute to maintaining participants' engagement over such a long period of time.

The different stages for the deployment of CS1 in the Spanish Pilot are the following:

1. Recruitment of citizens

Taking into account the target group and the kind food waste to be analyzed, the recruitment of citizens to participate in the project was made mainly through advertising placed in Zamudio stores where the type of salad object of the study is dispensed.

To complete the hiring process, the town council made direct phone calls to households in the municipality to guarantee a minimum number of people participating in the study. Study of the households captured to select approximately 10 households that define a representative sample of all citizens.

2. **Training** of households recruited to use the app for collecting the data to be analyzed. The *Appfood* is being used for that aim.
3. **Data collection and analysis.** Study of the data received throughout the first fortnight to establish the baseline.
4. **Intervention.** Training of households in the different solutions proposed through FOODRUS.
5. **Data collection and analysis.** Study of the data obtained in the app after the implementation of the solutions.

In addition to the monitoring of the families, waste generation habits will be also analysed by the Zamudio citizen e-cards (these cards are required to open the organic waste containers) and by using weight systems in containers and garbage trucks.

Members of the HORECA sector and commerce could also participate in this activity. These data will be used to quantify and monitor general waste of the Municipality, not focusing only on the waste related to salads consumption.

6. Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for the Spanish pilot.

The following KPIs are suggested to track CS1's progress and evaluate its influence on the development of the Spanish pilot. As said before, pilots are different in context and objectives. In this sense, a set of indicators is proposed for each pilot, so they can evaluate the evolution of CS1.

- Number of households reached - *expected a minimum of 10 households*.

- Amount of waste avoided - *expected 50% of waste avoided.*
- Behaviour change observed – qualitative assessment (self-reported by volunteers)
- Number of ecards users included in the study - *expected a minimum 10 ecards.*

DANISH PILOT – Meat and Fish

In the case of the Danish Pilot, the target group to participate in this activity are **university students** that eat in several canteens associated with the project. In this sense, the number of participants expected to take part actively in the CS1 is significantly bigger than in the case of the Spanish pilot.

1. Recruitment of students.

Several channels can be used to reach out to the participants. On the one hand, social networks are a suitable channel to reach the potential participants in the study due to its popularity among the student population.

In this sense, **social networks** (Instagram, Facebook or LinkedIn) are being used to disseminate online surveys and promote the activities carried out in the project, with the aim of reaching as many potential participants as possible. On the other hand, **advertising** physically placed at the canteens are also being used. Moreover, **partnerships** have been established with student associations to engage the students. In addition, mailing lists are used to spread information about the project-related activities, such as training actions, pop-up events or talks.

2. Training of students on the objectives of the project and the process itself, the aim of the CS, channels to be used for collecting the data, which kind of information is going to be collected.

3. Data collection and analysis.

Quantitative measurements will be conducted in several university canteens to monitor consumers behaviour in real context. In this sense a set of **surveys** will be conducted to collect information regarding the following issues:

- Food purchases.
- Amount of food served.
- Amount of food that is consumed.
- Amount of food that is thrown in the bins by consumers.

Consumers will also be surveyed to ascertain the reasons behind food waste.

In the Danish pilot other channels are being used for collecting the data from the participants. In this sense consumers are already using **QR codes** and an **App**, called *Foodop*, to report their opinions.

4. Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for the Danish pilot.

The following KPIs are suggested to track CS1's progress and evaluate its influence on the development of the Danish pilot. As said before, pilots are different in context and objectives. In this sense, a set of indicators is proposed for each pilot, so they can evaluate the evolution of CS1.

- Amount of waste avoided - *expected 50% waste avoided.*
- Number of students participating in the activities. - *expected at least 400 students.*

- Behaviour change observed regarding meat consumption - *expected at least 10% reduction of meat consumption.*
- Economic savings by avoiding food waste. 6-15% saved on the monthly spent on ingredients purchase.

SLOVAK PILOT - Bread

In the case of the Slovak pilot the target group to participate in this activity are **households**. The change of habits at consumer level is fundamental and can bring transformational change to the whole bread value chain. Behavioural change of the main bread consumers - households can positively affect the whole value chain backwards. Households are motivated by their positive contribution to the environment by reducing the carbon footprint and precious natural resources. Saving money spent on wasted food is another motivation for them. Better consumption habits adopted because of this solution can be expanded to other food commodities and communities.

1. Recruitment of citizens

In the case of the Slovak Pilot, a minimum of ten families need to be recruited. The monitoring period will be from November until April. For the recruitment of the families a website has been set up: www.jedloniejeodpad.sk. The research will be conducted in the Slovak language to facilitate communication with the families.

2. Training of the recruited households to explain the objectives of the research and the process itself, mainly the channels to be used for collecting the data, which kind of information is going to be collected and how.

Two trainings will be developed during the CS deployment: 1) a first training which will focus mainly on the aim of the research and the methodology of conducted data collection, and 2) a second training to present a set of solutions that households can choose to decrease bread waste.

3. Data collection and analysis.

For data collection each household will receive a separate recording Diary to be filled in on a regular basis for monitoring purposes, including practical steps for its keeping.

The Diary will be developed by Slovak pilot partners jointly in consultation with households.

4. Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for the Slovak pilot.

The following KPIs are suggested to track CS1's progress and evaluate its influence on the development of the Slovak pilot. As said before, pilots are different in context and objectives. In this sense, a set of indicators is proposed for each pilot, so they can evaluate the evolution of CS1.

- Number of households recruited and participating – *expected a minimum of 10 households.*
- Purchase avoided - *expected at least 10% reduction of purchases.*
- Amount of waste reduced - *expected at least 50% of bread waste reduced.*
- Behaviour change observed - qualitative assessment (self-reported by volunteers)
- Amount of packaging avoided or reduced – *expected at least 30% of packaging reduced.*

3.1.5. Schedule of the CS development

The deployment of CS will be explained in detail in D1.4. CS1 is scheduled in the following dates:

- Spanish Pilot: -November2022 - March2023.
- Danish Pilot: April 2022 - April 2023.
- Slovak Pilot: May 2022 - April 2023.

3.2. CS2. Working groups to co-create specific contents to develop the e-learning materials of T2.2.

In this section the methodology for the CS2 is explained. The application of this CS in FOODRUS project, and all the materials used, are described in depth in D2.2.

3.2.1. Objective

The main objective of this CS is to develop educational materials and a repository for all the identified solutions to be included in the FOODRUS e-learning platform.

Materials will be developed through a co-creation process and within co-creation working groups. The design of the materials will be the result of CS2 and CS9 (of Task 2.2 and Task 2.3).

Specific objectives can be set by each pilot, considering that they should contribute to:

- Identify all solutions that need to be included in the FOODRUS e-learning platform (also outside the ones identified in the GA).
- Narrow down and specify each solution that will be included in the platform.
- Set up working groups to work on the e-learning materials/content.
- Decide on the overall structure, target groups and main aims of the e-learning platform through co-creation workshops.
- Use of 2 living documents, and a Miro Board³ for the co-creation of the platform's content.
- Co-create the e-learning content for the FOODRUS e-learning platform based on partners' input.

In FOODRUS CS2 is led by Geonardo (GEO) for the three pilots. Each participating partner will work in the co-creation activity to develop the e-learning material. This activity is targeted at the consortium partners responsible for developing the e-learning content. Additional stakeholders, associated regions, or sister project partners may be later considered to assess the created content.

Regarding the target groups for the e-learning content, each included solution is foreseen to have different target audiences including children, citizens, academia, professionals, businesses, FOODRUS partners, etc.

³ <https://miro.com/>

3.2.2. Expected result

The expected result of this CS is the content generated by the participants in the working groups, to be included in the e-learning platform.

3.2.3. Stakeholder mapping - Participants in the development of the CS2

FOODRUS partners were identified to contribute to the development of the content with different roles, as shown in table 4.

Partners to participate in CS2 were identified based on the GA, the solutions calendar and other partners' feedback. They were contacted by email inviting them to participate in the CS2.

Table 4: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS2 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	ROLE
Geonardo (GEO)	Lead the CS to achieve the objectives.
Result Managers	Lead the CS working groups to provide the materials and organise any additional meetings and discussions. Result Managers were identified based on Grant Agreement (GA) and their role in WPs.
FOODRUS partners	Contribute to the development of the content and participate in the working groups. The working groups for each solution consist of partners who will be contributing to the e-learning content and work on related project results.

3.2.4. Methodology

The CS2 was developed using the following steps.

1. Setting up the working groups

First, the result managers identified all other relevant partners for each of the solution/result who should be involved in the co-working group.

2. Training/Information activities

Second, GEO organised an informational meeting to discuss questions related to the co-creation process of the e-learning platform. The meeting served to agree on and finalise the structure of the co-creation process.

Third, involved partners review and provide comments on the co-creation templates provided by GEO.

3. Co-creation process – content creation and analysis

The co-creation process for e-learning was carried out based on two aspects:

- 2 rounds of co-creation workshops.
- Use of two living documents (created by GEO) for content development.

CO-CREATION WORKSHOPS

The first round of co-creation workshops had the objective of starting a thought process, deciding on main themes, target groups, focus of the topics, overall structure, titles etc., of the platform.

The co-creation activities were carried out online using a Miro Board, and presentations.

The second round of co-creation workshop was focused on the final discussions related to the e-learning materials. In this sense, the sessions served to improve the content with the contribution of all the participants in the CS.

The dynamic of the working groups for generating content is described as follows:

- Throughout the process the partners must work in their Working groups (one for each solution). The working groups are led by their 'Result managers' to provide the materials and organise any additional meetings/discussion, if necessary, on their own.
- The CS leader (GEO in this case) must receive the learning materials in a structured way. To that aim a set of documents are provided to collect the information. Result managers and other involved partners must fill in these documents with their results by the agreed date.
- The CS leader (GEO in this case) will create the first draft of the e-learning materials ready for review based on the input received from the co-creation table.

4. Finalising the content and reviewing the platform

To complete the process the following activities must be completed:

- Fill in and finalise the 2 e-learning co-creation documents.
- Review all the materials received.
- Platform will be online and ready to be used/reviewed.

3.2.5. Planned Key performance Indicators (KPI)

The KPIs for the e-learning platform will be monitored through the registration feature. Some examples of KPIs can be the number of registrations, number of visits to the platform or the number of downloads.

3.2.6. Schedule of the CS development

The schedule foreseen for the CS2 is as follows:

- January 2022: Overview of co-creation template and identifying all relevant/contributing partners and solutions.
- May 2022: First round of co-creation workshop.
- July 2022: Platform is online with course overview and course structure.
- July 2022: First version of D2.2.
- November 2022: Second round of workshops with broader involvement of partners and with ready results.

- February 2023: Platform is ready to be used and reviewed with the available course content.
- March 2024: Platform is ready to be used with the available course content.

3.3. CS3. Working groups involving women to assess the gender dimension. Narrative production.

In this section the methodology for the CS3 is explained. The deployment of this CS in the three pilots will be further explained in D1.4.

3.3.1. Objective

Create qualitative data using the Narrative production method to assess the gender dimension. This activity should be conducted for each pilot with different groups of women, when possible.

CS3 specific objectives of each pilot are:

- **Spanish pilot:** Generate narratives about food waste from the feminine perspective and publish the narratives. The main objective is to understand the role of women in food shopping, cooking, sorting, and disposing of waste. The idea was to collect their experiences on managing food waste, what has changed from one generation to the next, how patterns are changing and what demands they make to the municipality.
- **Danish pilot:** Assess the gender dimension with university canteen users.
- **Slovak pilot:** Danish pilot's approach is the same as the Spanish pilot. The outcome of this activity will be a document describing and comparing women's various attitudes of the past and present shopping habits. Moreover, the data obtained will be also used for scientific articles.

3.3.2. Expected result

A publication about the perception of women on their role in food shopping, cooking, sorting, and disposing of food waste.

3.3.3. Stakeholder mapping - Participants in the development of the CS3

For a successful implementation of CS3 the involvement of a diversity of stakeholders with different roles is needed. Moreover, because they have different characteristics and objectives, the type of stakeholders may differ from one pilot to another. Table 5 summarizes the stakeholders' profiles and their roles in CS3.

Table 5: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS3 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SPANISH PILOT	DANISH PILOT	SLOVAK PILOT	ROLE
Pilot Leaders	Municipality of Zamudio	University of Copenhagen	Slovak University of Agriculture	Recruitment of participants. Training activities. Engagement activities. Data collection.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SPANISH PILOT	DANISH PILOT	SLOVAK PILOT	ROLE
Researchers of FOODRUS	University of Deusto. BCC.	University of Copenhagen	Slovak University of Agriculture.	Data collection Information analysis
FOODRUS partners			SUA, NewEdu, Free Food + Senické pekárne	Recruitment of participants. Data providers. Data collection.
Women	The Zamudio Women's Association ("Asociación de mujeres de Zamudio") is taking part in the activity. In particular, women over 60 years old are involved.	Students of the canteens.	Women of different types: women as housewives, women responsible for cooking and shopping coming from various backgrounds.	Data providers (qualitative information)

3.3.4. Methodology

The Narrative Production Methodology described below will be used in two pilots:

Narrative productions are hybrid texts that are created through a series of contacts between 'researchers' and 'participants.' These conversations are then turned into a text that reflects the participant's view of a given topic. The conversations are recorded by the researcher, who then writes the narrative text from the first-person point of view. The text is interchanged with the interviewee as many times as necessary to agree on the final story.⁴

The general procedure consists of the following steps:

1. First meeting. In this meeting the CS leaders will provide all the participants (women) with the information about the process: methods, objectives, planning, etc.
2. Individual sessions. Individual sessions will be carried out with the participants to collect information. The sessions last 30-40 minutes on average and are recorded with the participants' permission.
3. Writing of the narrative text. This task consists of listening to each of the interviews and textualization.

This can be made in two different forms:

- a) Transcribe literally each session and then try to put the ideas in a readable order, giving a narrative character to the text.
 - b) Writing down ideas into a readable and understandable narrative style while listening to the recordings.
4. Submission of the first version: The narrative drafts are sent to each participant via *WhatsApp*.

⁴ Ramírez-March, Á., & Montenegro, M. (2021). On narrativity, knowledge production, and social change: a diffractive encounter between the Narrative Productions methodology and Participatory Action-Research. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 1-12.

5. **Validation:** New individual sessions are carried out with each of the participants to validate the final Narrative production. Participants provide their input, changes, and mention what they want to remove. (As many text corrections and validation sessions as necessary).

The narrative production methodology is being applied in the Spanish and in the Slovak pilot. In the Danish pilot a different approach will be used to meet the gender dimension in food waste. The methodology for the implementation of the CS3 in the three pilots is described below.

SPANISH PILOT

In the case of the Spanish pilot, the CS3 is developed in the municipality of Zamudio.

The Zamudio Women's Association ("Asociación de mujeres de Zamudio") took part in the activity. In this case in particular, women over 60 years old were involved. The process carried out completed all the steps of the methodology.

In this case seven women belonging to the Association participated in the process. The researchers contacted directly with the Association to select the participants.

At the first meeting the researchers explained the project, the objectives and the methodology, and the individual sessions with each of the selected women were scheduled. Then seven personal interviews were conducted with the women from the Zamudio Women Association participating in the CS.

The script for the interviews used in the Spanish pilot can be found in Annex 3.1.

Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for CS3 in the Spanish pilot.

The only KPI possible is the number of interviews, although it is not very relevant considering it involves qualitative data.

Number of interviews in the Spanish Pilot: 7 interviews with women.

DANISH PILOT

In this case of the Danish pilot, the qualitative surveys carried out in CS1 will be used to consider the gender dimension within the student population by analysing data from a gender perspective. In this sense, the surveys "*Survey on consumers intention and motivation of buying surplus food in canteens*" and "*Survey on consumers food choice motives and food waste behaviour in university canteens*" will consider the gender dimension in the analysis of surveys.

Moreover, quantitative monitoring data and awareness raising interventions will take place at the university canteens applying a mixed methods research approach.

Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for CS3 in the Danish pilot.

The only KPI possible is the number of interviews, although it is not very relevant considering it involves qualitative data.

Danish Pilot: Analyse the gender dimension through the respondents to the surveys - *expected at least 400 students*.

SLOVAK PILOT

As well as in the Spanish pilot, the narrative production methodology is used in the Slovak pilot. In this case the groups of women participating in the CS are a group of housewives and women responsible for cooking and shopping coming from various backgrounds. Working groups involving women will be created to assess the gender dimension.

Women are contacted directly and invited to participate in the research. Moreover, other methods to recruit women can be used, like targeted advertisements or participating in specific events.

Several activities with the working groups are planned for recruitment and data collection:

- Workshops training women on start-ups.
- Online workshop for women, “bread as a part of healthy lifestyle”. Presentation and discussion with a nutrition scientist showing the positive and negative aspects of eating various types of bread.
- Discussion on nutritional aspects of various types of bread consumption.
- Women networking and training meeting during *Degustorium* conference.
- Dedicated awareness campaign to women as main responsible for groceries and cooking.
- Workshops with charity working with women.
- Video with 10 questions addressed to women.
- Interviews with women on their perspective and experience.

Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for CS3 in the Slovak pilot.

The KPIs for the Slovak pilot are the following:

Slovak Pilot:

- Number of participants: 7-10 interviews with women.
- Number of events/workshops: 4 events/workshops organised.

3.3.5. Schedule of the CS development

- Spanish Pilot: Interviews were conducted between 22nd of November 2021 and the 7th of February 2022.
- Danish Pilot: The surveys are expected to be conducted in 2022 and 2023.
- Slovak Pilot: From May 2022 onwards.

3.4. CS4. Fiscal instruments and tax incentives.

This section describes the methodology for developing CS4.

3.4.1. Objective

The main objective of this CS is to discuss the fiscal instruments (taxes, incentives...) proposed in T4.4 and test the real incidence of the tax incentives in different contexts such as: individuals and families, commerce, and industry (E.g., PAYT in the Spanish pilot). Capacity building strategies from T4.2 (crowdfunding, crowdlending, SIBs, microcredits, crowd-shared capital, donations...) and relationship with taxes and tax incentives, will also be assessed.

It is recommended that each Pilot conducts this activity, as there are fiscal differences per region. However, FOODRUS partners UD and FEBEA, will help develop the script for the focus groups for each pilot and analyse the results.

Each pilot can have several **specific objectives**. The specific objectives for the Spanish and the Danish pilots are described as follows.

- **Spanish Pilot:** The Spanish pilot will work on fiscal measures: proposals and views. It is understood that these fiscal measures should include those that entail an additional fiscal cost (taxes and/or fees) for citizens and companies, as well as tax rebates and incentives or other types of incentives (free material, gifts, raffles, awards, etc.).

Specific objectives to be attached in the Spanish pilot:

- Identify and assess the incentive character of fiscal measures on final consumers, their limitations and relative weight in a larger set of public/legal measures.
 - Identify the practical difficulties in implementing such incentives for citizenship.
 - Identifying positive levers and practical opportunities for the implementation of such incentives for citizenship.
 - Identify and assess the possibilities for citizen pressure on companies on these issues.
- **Danish Pilot:** The Danish pilot aims to identify hotspot barriers and the enabling policy instruments within the existing policy regime, to support local business ecosystems solving the challenges of the global food system. To that aim they will combine environmental, economic, and social cost-benefit analysis.

This will involve analysis of existing and alternative policy instruments such as subsidies, taxes, carbon credits to correct for policy and markets' failures to restore and regenerate the planetary boundaries. Moreover, the identification of fiscal instruments that influence behaviours by "getting the prices right" and create powerful incentives for producers, consumers, and investors.

This will help to interact in a concerted manner to reach climate neutral and zero waste circular food systems that exchange resources with the natural environment, designed to deliver soil health and food safety for future generations.

3.4.2. Expected result

Briefing/report and recommendations, e-learning material, regarding fiscal instruments for reducing FW and FL. This activity is connected to R10 - toolkits for fiscal instruments.

3.4.3. Stakeholder Mapping - Participants in the development of the CS4

For a successful implementation of CS4 the involvement of a diversity of stakeholders with different roles is needed. The type of stakeholders may differ from one pilot to another.

In table 6 a list of recommended stakeholders is provided. In the Spanish pilot this activity is targeted to associations, foundations, federations, confederations, and non-formal organisations.

Table 6: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS4 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SPANISH PILOT	DANISH PILOT	ROLE
Pilot Leaders	Municipality of Zamudio	University of Copenhagen	Recruitment of participants. Training activities. Engagement activities. Data collection.
Researchers of FOODRUS	University of Deusto. BCC.	University of Copenhagen	Data collection Information analysis
FOODRUS partners			Recruitment of participants. Data providers. Data collection.
Other stakeholders		Consumers in general, covering a wide range and diversity of stakeholders.	Data providers (qualitative information)
Other stakeholders	Consumers, women and housewives, families, family associations in educational establishments running canteens.		Data providers (qualitative information)
	Social and civic representatives of neighbourhoods, districts, cities, associations of municipalities.		
	Consumption circles (those informal networks of consumers in direct contact with local producers in the km0 philosophy, managing the purchase and distribution of baskets of seasonal agricultural products on a regular basis).		
	Environmentalists, protection of the environment, promotion of the rural environment.		

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SPANISH PILOT	DANISH PILOT	ROLE
	<p>Representative organisations of the social and solidarity economy and social enterprises. Other entities that, although they do not represent these groups, do work with them directly and may have a qualified opinion.</p>		
	<p>In general, any other organised, but not necessarily formal, group with leadership in the geographic area of interest because of its qualified opinion on the matter.</p>		

NOTE: It is not necessary to invite all these types of organisations, but only those that are most representative or exist in the context of each pilot.

3.4.4. Methodology

SPANISH PILOT

1. Recruitment of participants.

- Determine the entities that, considering the context of the pilot, must be invited. A variety of stakeholders must be represented, according to the list suggested in the "Target group" section of this CS. In other words, it is not necessary to have one representative from each target group, but at least three or four of these groups, in order to guarantee a diversity of points of view and sensitivities.
- Choose the most appropriate person - from within the invited organisations - to participate in the session.
- Make sure that the participants are diverse in terms of age, education, and particularly gender. In general, it is considered gender-balanced if there is a 60%-40% representation. In some cases, there could be a greater inclination towards women (due to the profile of the invited organisations where there are usually more women working) and in that case, participation of more than 60% women would be accepted.
- Send formal personalised invitation with explanation of objectives and timetable, including an informed consent to sign. The invitations will be sent by e-mail to the potential participants.
- Constitution of the group, ensuring variety in the profile of the participants, with a minimum of 4/5 and a maximum of 8/10 participants, necessarily from different organisations, even if they belong to the same target group profile (see the first step).

2. Training

People participating in the CS will receive information and training about the data collection methods to be used. Moreover, information regarding the project and its objectives will be provided.

3. Data collection and analysis.

The focus group methodology explained in section 3 is proposed for this activity.

One session with a sufficiently diverse group would be adequate, although it is up to the pilot to decide whether to create two groups to invite more participants. Face-to-face focus groups are recommended, except in cases of *force majeure* (for example the recent pandemic situation).

Recommended duration of the session: two hours with an informal break of 15 minutes maximum (total: 2.15 hours).

The session will be conducted by people involved in the pilot and knowledgeable about the FOODRUS project adopting different roles.

- **Moderator:** Dynamizes the different phases of the session, raises the questions in each round and gives the floor to the participants in no particular order, ensuring that they participate in an atmosphere of cordiality and collaboration, manages the time for participation (suggestion of 1 minute per participant, who can then be called to speak again), channelling the conversation, dead time, reiterations, deviations from the subject to be dealt with, always with flexibility and respect.
- **Controller/support:** Support to the moderator in a dual moderation. Checks that all points have been addressed, that everyone participates, controls the time, and the collaborative environment, picks up other topics not directly related to the question to launch them in another more appropriate round (if considered appropriate).
- **Secretary/note taker:** Takes notes of what was shared and writes the final report, supported by a possible voice recording of the session (with informed consent).

These three roles do not have to express their opinion or debate, nor do they have to be right or wrong on the issues discussed. It is important that all the participants feel that their opinions are valued, listened to and taken positively. Therefore, they should be aware of possible tensions and/or negative comments in order to neutralise them appropriately.

The session protocol can be summarized in the following 5 steps:

A. Before the session:

- Short presentation of the project and the participants.
- Informed consent, including permission for voice recording of the session.
- Voice recording system check.
- List of questions.

B. Introduction to the session:

- Brief presentation of the project and call for a dialogue and listening attitude (3 minutes).
- Review of informed consent, and specifically for voice recording of the session (2 minutes).
- Introduction of the participants (10 minutes): each participant introduces him/herself briefly so that the rest of the participants can get to know his/her background. We recommend that each person has a name sign on the table to help the rest of the participants to interact in a more personalised way.

C. Participation rounds: In each round,

- The moderator asks the question and invites the participants to speak in no particular order, ensuring that everyone participates in an atmosphere of cordiality and collaboration.
- There are four rounds, each lasting 25 minutes, focusing on the following questions:

1. What is your opinion on the effectiveness of fiscal measures to reduce food waste in final consumers? What fiscal measures would you recommend? What do you consider to be the relevance of these fiscal measures in the set of public/legal measures?
2. What do you consider to be the practical difficulties in implementing these tax incentives for citizens?
3. What do you see as the positive drivers and practical opportunities for the implementation of such incentives for citizenship?
4. What do you think are the real possibilities for citizen pressure on companies on these issues?

D. Closing and thanks (5 minutes)

E. After the session:

- Writing the final report, ordered according to four key questions.
- Sending to WP4 coordinator

4. Planned Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The following KPIs are suggested to track CS4's progress and evaluate its influence on the development of the Spanish pilot.

- Gender balance among participants (%) - *at least 60%-40 % (both men and women).*
- Number of people participating in the activity.
- Number of entities represented in the activity and types - *at least 10 different entities representing the public, private and social sectors.*
- Number of ideas on fiscal measures to reduce FW at the final customer level - *Identification of at least 6 ideas.*
- Number of ideas to measure the effectiveness of fiscal measures to reduce food waste in final consumers - *Identification of at least 6 ideas.*
- Number of barriers identified to the implementation of tax incentives for citizenship - *identification of at least 8 ideas.*
- Number of positive levers and practical opportunities for the implementation of tax incentives for citizenship - *Identification of at least 8 ideas.*
- Number of ideas on the real possibilities for citizen pressure on companies on these issues - *Identification of at least 8 ideas.*

DANISH PILOT

1. Recruitment of participants.

The Danish pilot will recruit participants for this CS in several ways. On the one hand, social networks are a suitable channel to reach the potential participants in the study, consumers. On the other hand, other more personalised recruitment methods, such as mailing or direct invitations can be suitable for other kinds of stakeholders, professionals for example.

2. Data collection.

In the case of the Danish pilot, the data needed is collected through several surveys. In this sense, the Danish pilot has completed seven surveys to analyse social readiness level of citizen-consumers to support the transition into resilient food systems.

Additionally, the Danish Pilot leader will host several workshops on Food waste hierarchy and circular economy solutions to present and discuss current and alternative regulatory barriers and enablers for reaching Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12.3 and associated avoidance of environmental degradation. The workshops aim to include knowledge from all pilots on existing and alternative fiscal instruments for incentivising behavioural change.

3. Planned Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The following KPIs are suggested to track CS4's progress and evaluate its influence on the development of the Danish pilot.

- Survey on consumers intention and motivation of buying surplus food in canteens - *minimum 400 respondents.*
- Survey on consumers knowledge about and willingness to buy dairy products close to the best before date in Denmark - *minimum 400 respondents.*
- Survey on consumers' willingness to buy meat products close to the expiry date in Denmark - *minimum 400 respondents.*
- Survey on consumers' food choice motives and food waste behaviour in university canteens - *minimum 400 respondents.*
- Consumer attitude toward upcycled food in four different European countries - *minimum 400 respondents.*

3.5. CS5. Co-creative citizen science activity.

This section describes the methodology for developing CS5. The CS will be explained in detail in D1.1 where the implementation of this activity is described. The responsible of the design and development of this CS in the context of the FOODRUS project has been DEUSTO University.

3.5.1. Objective

The main objective of CS5 is to involve all stakeholders of the project in the design of the technological and social solutions of the project.

Some specific objectives can be defined:

- Detect the expectations that each stakeholder has in each solution to ensure that each stakeholder knows the needs, misgivings, and desires of the rest of the stakeholders that participate in the supply chain.
- Determine which stakeholder will be a direct user of the solution and which stakeholder has an indirect interest, either during its use or during its design or development.
- Identify the aspects of each solution that are common to any type of product or pilot, and the aspects that are particular or specific to a particular product.
- Detect the need to incorporate new stakeholders or technological suppliers.

- Define the functional requirements of each solution: what will be its objective, who will be the user, how will it be used, what are the expected results, etc.
- Define the scope of the pilots along the supply chains: the products, by-products or secondary products, their routes and points of exchange, the data or information that each stakeholder must provide and exchange, the technological systems or devices that will be necessary, the interoperability between systems or databases, planning the validation of the solutions, etc.
- Test and evaluate the feedback of the stakeholders regarding the (i) performance of the solutions, (ii) the limits or restrictions, (iii) the fulfilment of expectations, and (iv) the improvements or future actions.

3.5.2. Expected result

A description of a high-level design for each solution of the FOODRUS project.

3.5.3. Stakeholder Mapping - Participants in the development of the CS5

The target group of this activity for all the pilots are the **internal stakeholders of the project**, both the direct users of the solutions and the technology or work methodologies suppliers.

This CS activity has many phases. Some phases are used in various co-creation activities and some others do not. Therefore, the participants in the development of the CS are all stakeholders of the project but in different phases. Table 7 summarizes the stakeholders participating in this CS and their roles.

Table 7: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS5 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	ROLE
University of Deusto	CS design. CS leader. Data collection.
All FOODRUS partners	Participants in the activities.

3.5.4. Methodology

To complete the CS5 five phases must be covered. The phases are divided as follows:

- **Phase 1.**

In this first phase, the GA is analyzed in order to identify: (i) the results (R) that have been set as objectives in the FOODRUS project, (ii) the solutions (S) to be developed to achieve those results, (iii) the outputs expected from each solution (OP), and (iv) the pilots and partners that are called to participate in each of them. This analysis is captured in an outline document that is shared with the pilot managers, who in turn share it with their stakeholders. The purpose of this first phase is to make each stakeholder aware of the solutions in which they are involved, and to detect whether the project will indeed be able to involve the necessary partners. This phase also serves to collect the expectations and priority objectives of each pilot.

- **Phase 2.**

Workshops must be organized, where solution managers present the solution to all partners, explaining the expected objectives of each solution and the expected outputs.

The purpose of this phase is to give the opportunity to ‘solution managers’ to explain the solutions from their technical or knowledge perspective. Moreover, this phase can serve to collect the first feedback from the stakeholders that will be involved in the process, as well as the confirmation of their participation in the co-design and validation activities. To that aim, any co-working tool can be used, for example digital whiteboards like *Miro*⁵ to facilitate and promote the exchange of ideas.

- **Phase 3.**

In this phase the solution manager collects all feedback given by the project partners and prepares a document explaining the solution design. The document should have a first part describing the solution as it is for any type of product or Pilot. The second part of the document would have a functional design of the solution for each Pilot. The purpose of this phase is also to agree among all the participants in a solution about the scope and the main use cases of the solution, as an input for D1.2 where functional requirements will be detailed.

- **Phase 4.**

These documents generated are edited in co-working meetings or peer to peer interviews led by solution managers with related stakeholders, as the basis for the design of use cases of each solution.

Each person responsible for each solution organizes different work sessions with the partners to define the scope of the solution. The working sessions can be collective among several partners or individuals, depending on the details to be specified, and the availability of the partners.

Solutions can be very different, some of them are ICT based solutions and others are social or methodical solutions. They may need different timing for each phase. Moreover, the language used in co-creation activities is key, as achieving a common understanding is very difficult in a non-mother language. This means that some solution managers will reach better to stakeholders of their own country than others. Pilot managers are key in these cases, as they should have the role of the solution manager but without their skills. This could delay the co-creation activity for those pilots that will use the pilot coordinators as “representatives” of the solution managers. Note that this fact should be considered in the planification of further design and development activities.

- **Phase 5.**

Probably the most important phase is the evaluation of what has been co-created. This phase will test and evaluate the feedback of the stakeholders regarding at least four aspects:

- The performance of the co-created solution,
- The limits or restrictions of the solution regarding their specific needs.

⁵ <https://miro.com/>

- The improvements or future actions.
- The potential to extend the solution to other use cases (own and sectorial use cases).
- This phase will be done with two specific activities: first, a survey will get the mentioned feedback. Then all the feedback will be shared and discussed in a collaborative workshop.

3.5.5. Planned Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Number of people participating in the activity - *expected at least 20 people*.
- Number of entities represented in the activity and types - *expected at least 20 entities*.

3.5.6. Schedule of the CS development

Spanish pilot: Has completed phases 1-3, phase 4 is currently undergoing (Below) and phase 5 will be completed when the solutions will be deployed.

Danish pilot: Has organized 8 workshops with stakeholders about the design and implementation of the solutions.

Slovak pilot: Has worked on analyzing the solutions that can be applied in pilots and is performing a series of workshops and co-creation events to determine the implementations of the solutions. The responsible persons for each solution have been determined.

- July 2021 to September 2021: Phase 1. All the pilots have completed this phase.
- October 2021 to November 2021: Phase 2. The Spanish pilot completed this phase. Danish and Slovak pilots are still working on it.
- December 2021: Phase 3. The Spanish pilot completed this phase. Danish and Slovak pilots are still working on it.
- January 2022 to April 2022: Phase 4. All pilots are still working on this phase.
- Phase 5. This phase will be completed as soon as solutions are developed and deployed.

3.6. CS6. Working groups to discuss the methodology for the quantification of food losses and waste (UD/AIN).

This section describes the methodology for developing CS6.

3.6.1. Objective

The objective of CS6 is to discuss the methodology for the quantification of food losses and waste and its environmental, social and economic impacts, as well as the evaluation of prevention actions. A short list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to quantify food waste and food loss will be also defined.

3.6.2. Expected result

A validated list of KPIs to quantify food waste and food loss.

3.6.3. Stakeholder Mapping - Participants in the development of the CS6

The target group of this activity are waste generators in the food supply chains (producers, processors, distributors, retailers, and HORECA), and end consumers (both in households and in HORECA). In general, FOODRUS partners and stakeholders representing the 3 different food value chains in the pilots and experts are aimed to participate in the CS6. Table 8 summarizes the stakeholder's profiles to participate in this CS.

Table 8: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS6 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	ROLE
University of Deusto AIN	CS leaders. Recruitment of participants. Data collection
FOODRUS partners	Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers.
Pilot leaders	Recruitment of participants Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers.
Pilot's food value chain stakeholders	Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers.
Other experts (professionals, scientists, consumers)	Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers

3.6.4. Methodology

The methodology for completing CS6 is described now in a general manner.

1. Recruitment of participants.

The recruitment of participants will be made by direct invitations to the stakeholders.

A good starting point could be the identification of existing working groups in the pilots by Pilot Coordinators and open call for the configuration of the Advisory Board (AB) for FLW quantification (including sister projects⁶).

2. Data collection and analysis.

For the data collection a combination of methods can be used, such as surveys, workshops or interviews.

- Firstly, technical work must be carried out to find existing methodologies and indicators already in use. In this sense, different sources of information should be analysed:
 - Revision of European Legislation & methods (quantitative & qualitative).

⁶ FOODRUS' sister projects are: [Co-fresh](#); [Fairchain](#); [Lowinfood](#) and [Ploutos](#).

- Creation of the KPIs long list (based on pre-list defined in the proposal and literature).
- Co-creation process for KPIs definition:
 - Consultation to experts (AB) to agree on the long list, to evaluate additional KPIs (if necessary) and to create the final short list.
 - Creation of the survey for stakeholders to assess the applicability of the KPIs.
 - Organisation and execution of the workshop on KPIs with stakeholders and experts to adapt the previous results for social use and explain the AHP methodology.
 - Creation of the AHP survey to stakeholders and experts.
- Short list technical work:
 - Elaboration of the KPIs sheets explaining the calculation methodology for each KPI.
- Co-creation process for KPIs implementation:
 - Pilot working groups to discuss the short list, calculation methods in each pilot and their link to regional SDGs.
- Implementation and revision of the process.

3.6.5. Planned Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The measures to monitor the CS are defined below, they can be adapted by each pilot's specific objectives.

- Recruitment for KPIs identification process:
 - 28 people (68% women, 32% men) from 27 institutions agreed on participating in the process.
 - 21 people (71% women, 29% men) from 21 institutions finally participated at some stage of the process.
- A total of 44 different institutions were involved and contributed along the **Co-creation process** for KPIs definition:
 - 22 institutions answered to the first survey (KPIs long list).
 - 12 stakeholders from the FOODRUS pilots answered to the second survey.
 - 40 experts (representing 31 different institutions) participated in the workshop.
 - 19 institutions answered to the third survey (AHP).
- The short list of the KPIs is **applicable** to the different **stages of a FVC** at the following levels:
 - Production stage: 72%
 - Processing stage: 72%
 - Distribution stage: 38%
 - Retail stage: 60%
 - Consumption stage: 47%
 - Waste management stage: 33%

- The short list of the KPIs is **applicable** to the different **pilots** at the following levels:
 - Spanish pilot: 48%
 - Slovak pilot: 47%
 - Danish pilot: 88%
- The **representativeness** of the stakeholders participating in the process according to the different **stages of a FVC** they belong to, is:
 - Production stage: 17%
 - Processing stage: 17%
 - Distribution stage: 9%
 - Retail stage: 17%
 - Consumption stage: 35%
 - Waste management stage: 4%
- The **representativeness** of the stakeholders participating in the process according to the different **pilots** they belong to, is:
 - Spanish pilot: 70%
 - Slovak pilot: 100%
 - Danish pilot: 83%

3.6.6. Schedule of the CS development

All pilots

- November 2020 to May 2021: Initial technical work.
- May 2021 to December 2021: Co-creation process for KPIs definition.
- March 2022 to June 2022: Short list technical work.
- April 2022 to June 2022: Co-creation process for KPIs implementation.
- June 2022 to the end of the project: Implementation and revision of the process.

3.7. CS7. Working groups to discuss the result of the baseline, assess the causes and the existing solutions to identify potential barriers and solutions to be implemented following the methodology described in T4.1.

This section describes the methodology for developing CS7.

3.7.1. Objective

This activity is a follow-up on citizen science activities 6 and 7. The main objective is to have a methodology for scouting, attracting, and implementing prototypes (based on the solutions) by all living labs. For those solutions that can be immediately implemented and with low cost there is a budget to uptake them adapted to the pilot

cases. For example, solutions to improve food conservation at schools, logistics and storage solutions for food donation involving volunteers or associations as taxi drivers.

3.7.2. Expected result

A solutions portfolio to be assessed in Task 4.2 to find building capacity strategies for the short-medium term.

3.7.3. Stakeholder mapping - Participants in the development of the CS7

In the development of CS7 entrepreneurs and start-ups will be involved in scouting, attracting, and implementing prototypes to measure the KPIs and for the 23 solutions by means of living labs. The stakeholders of each pilot will also participate in the CS7. Table 9 summarizes the stakeholder's profiles to participate in this CS.

Table 9: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS7 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	ROLE
Pilot Leaders	Recruitment of participants. Data collection
Stakeholders of each pilot	Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers.
Entrepreneurs	Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers.
Start-ups	Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers.

3.7.4. Methodology

1. Recruitment of participants

Participants entrepreneurs, start-ups, stakeholders, can be recruited using different channels, for example open calls or direct invitations.

2. Data collection

Working groups will be created with the participants to discuss successful cases, identify new models and reflect on the models themselves, social canvas, market analysis to foster the offer and demand, identify gaps.

3.7.5. Planned Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The following KPIs are suggested to track CS7's progress and evaluate its impact.

- Number of people participating in the activity - *at least 25 people*.
- Number of entities represented in the activity and types - *at least 25 entities*.
- Number of ideas identified to reduce food waste - *a minimum of 6 ideas*.

3.7.6. Schedule of the CS development

Each pilot coordinator must determine the most appropriate moment to carry out the activity.

3.8. CS8. A participatory process to define the municipal tax of the PAYT considering the impact of FW prevention.

This section describes the methodology for developing CS8.

3.8.1. Objective

The main objective of this CS is to define the municipal tax considering the impact of FW prevention by a participative process.

The specific objectives for each pilot are:

- **Spanish Pilot:** In the case of the Spanish pilot, to conduct a participatory process with citizens to define the municipal tax considering the impact of FW prevention. Additionally other specific objective is defined:
 - Include in the current PAYT calculation the food waste variable.
- **Danish Pilot:** In the case of the Danish pilot, the main objective is to conduct a participatory process with students from the canteen to raise awareness about food waste, with a system that charges if there is food waste, through zero waste cooking events and nudging interventions in the canteens. Instead of taxes the Danish Pilot applies a reduced-price approach on surplus food selling in the canteens. Willingness to pay for surplus foods surveys have been conducted to support the design of to-go / last mile options.
- **Slovak Pilot:** This activity cannot be conducted in the Slovak pilot because the PAYT system cannot be implemented in this pilot.

3.8.2. Expected result

Spanish Pilot: Raise awareness among citizens about recycling using the PAYT system.

Danish Pilot: Raise awareness about reducing food waste.

Slovak Pilot: Cannot conduct this activity as they cannot apply a PAYT system in their pilot.

3.8.3. Stakeholder mapping - Participants in the development of the CS8

In the development of CS8 several stakeholders will be involved. Table 10 summarizes the stakeholder's profiles to participate in this CS.

Table 10: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS8 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SPANISH PILOT	DANISH PILOT	ROLE
Pilot Leaders	Municipality of Zamudio	University of Copenhagen	Recruitment of participants. Development of the CS Data collection Communication activities
	Citizens of the Zamudio municipality		Participate in the activities as data providers.
Citizens		Students eating at the canteen	Participate in intervention studies carried out via the implementation of different nudging strategies and surveys mapping, e.g. motivations for behavioural changes.
Other FOODRUS partners			Give technical support.

3.8.4. Methodology

In this section the methodology for the Spanish and the Danish pilot is described.

SPANISH PILOT

1. Recruitment of participants

In the case of the Spanish pilot the recruitment of the participants in the CS8 will be carried out by the City Council. To that aim the City Council will use their own communication channels, including its monthly magazine and the citizen app.

2. Activities and data collection

The participative process in the Spanish pilot will be led by Zamudio's City Council and several meetings with the participants will be held to discuss the different options and finally reach an agreement. In this sense, the process will be divided into the following steps:

- Inform the participants. The purpose of including the food waste variable in the distribution rates calculation as well as the integration process are presented.
- Discussion and collection of the different points of view of the participants in the process.
- Preparation of proposals for the introduction of food waste in the PAYT.
- Decision making.

3. Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for the Spanish pilot.

The following KPIs are foreseen to monitor the implementation of CS8 in the Spanish pilot.

- Number of participants in the participatory process - *at least 20 people*.
- Number of participative processes conducted - *at least 1*.

DANISH PILOT

1. Recruitment of participants

The Danish pilot will recruit participants for this CS in several ways. On the one hand, social networks are a suitable channel to reach the potential participants in the study, consumers. On the other hand, other methods such as advertising in the canteens can also be used.

2. Activities and data collection

Intervention studies will be carried out via the implementation of different nudging strategies and surveys mapping, e.g. motivations for behavioural changes.

3. Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for the Danish pilot.

The following KPIs are foreseen to monitor the implementation of CS8 in the Spanish pilot.

- Number of respondents - expected at least 400 respondents.
- Number of participative processes conducted - at least 1.

3.8.5. Schedule of the CS development

Each pilot must determine the most appropriate moment to carry out the activity.

3.9. CS9. Actions to develop healthy and sustainable diets. Actions to develop and deploy a nutritionally balanced gastronomic and sustainable guideline in real context.

This section describes the methodology for developing CS9.

3.9.1. Objective

The main goal of CS9 is to **promote healthy and sustainable diets** within the population, favouring **strategies (i.e., culinary strategies)** to manage discards produced at home and hence, reducing food waste.

Specific objectives can be established for each pilot considering their specificities and needs:

- **Spanish pilot:** Some specific objectives have been set for the Spanish pilot:
 - To develop nutritionally balanced gastronomic and sustainable guidelines that could be used by citizens (families/canteens).
 - To conduct a methodology that allows to analyze the impact of healthy and sustainable diets on citizen's health (children).
- **Danish pilot:** The Danish pilot's main objective is to increase knowledge and awareness to avoid FW and adopt more sustainable habits by promoting plant-based diets while minimizing the intake of animal protein, meat and fish, at the canteens.

To that aim, the following specific objectives have been set:

- Co-creation in food innovation hubs.

- Zero waste cooking skills development.
- Awareness raising around the opportunity of marketing zero waste solutions as a new dimension of the taste of sustainability.
- Cooking skills development boosting the transition to plant-based diet menu designs
- Umami in plant-based cooking.
- Knowledgebase development on health-aspects of plant-based servings.
- **Slovak pilot:** The main objective of the Slovak pilot is to study the cultural and social value of bread and analyze retail and consumer behaviour towards bakery products through surveys.

In this case other specific objectives have also been set:

- Gather information and analyze retail and consumer behaviour towards bakery products in cooperation with associated supermarkets.
- Raise awareness and improve understanding of FW issues through the organization of Zero Waste events with zero waste chefs to (Zero Waste brunches 09/2021 and 09/2022, Degustorium conference in 05/ 2022).
- Research the nutritional value of different bread and bakery products (to be done in cooperation with nutritionists and will be part of the Zero Waste cookbook focused on bread).
- Analyze consumption patterns and behaviours in cooperation with supermarkets and through collecting data from 2 surveys: households measuring waste and survey to gather data for the cookbook.
- To help schools in the adoption of methodologies and solutions on how to incorporate healthy and sustainable eating culture at schools. Work with consumer expectations of an increasing list of different bread types, rolls, baguettes, pastry.

3.9.2. Expected result

- Recipe book: healthy and sustainable recipes including discarded food by-products in kitchens (School specific).
- Awareness raising and behavioural change among target groups.

3.9.3. Stakeholder mapping - Participants in the development of the CS9

In general, this activity targets citizens (families, students, professionals from canteens, consumers, civil society, stakeholders,...), children and teachers (programs to tackle the problem of FWL in the curriculum - distribute e-learning materials), municipalities (have data regarding FW collection from school canteens), retail, citizens (hot spot); interest groups of the national climate centre, chefs, cooks and other downstream kitchen customers, employees at JTK (Danish Pilot).

- Pilot participants: **interviews.**
- Citizens/students/families/professional chefs from school canteens: **data recording.**
- Researchers of FOODRUS: **data analyses.**

- JTK and UCHP (Copenhagen University / formerly Aarhus University (AU)), the national climate centre and Aarhus University student association.

Table 11 summarizes the stakeholder's profiles to participate in this CS.

Table 11: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS9 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SPANISH PILOT	DANISH PILOT	SLOVAK PILOT	ROLE
Pilot Leaders	Municipality of Zamudio	University of Copenhagen	Slovak University of Agriculture	Recruitment of participants. Training activities. Engagement activities. Data collection. Interaction with participants Monitoring.
Researchers of FOODRUS	BCC.	University of Copenhagen BCC Jespers Torvekøkken	Slovak University of Agriculture. BCC	Recruitment of participants. Methodology. Data analysis. Responsible for designing and developing the activities. Interaction with citizens (training activities, monitoring).
Chefs and other professionals				Participate in the activities (for example showcookings) Give professional advice.
Other participants	School canteen users (Families. School in Zamudio (Colegio Vizcaya). Professionals from Canteens Citizens of Zamudio	Canteen users. Professionals from Canteens	Families	Participate in the activities (workshops, training activities, etc). Data providers (Surveys, workshops, etc.)

3.9.4. Methodology

In this section the methodology for developing the CS9 in the three pilots is described. The deployment of the CS9 in each pilot will be further explained in D1.4.

SPANISH PILOT

The methodology of this CS in the case of the Spanish pilot consisted of creating a guideline for families providing useful information regarding healthy and sustainable diets. The guideline also provided families with a number of recipes that aimed to promote food waste valorization at households.

1. Recruitment of participants

The coordinators of each pilot have decided the best way to recruit participants.

In the Spanish pilot the main intervention was conducted in a school in Zamudio namely “Colegio Vizcaya”. In this sense the managers at the school were contacted directly by the personnel of the Zamudio Council and the researchers of BCC.

The school manager launched a call for families to participate in a culinary workshop focused on discard management.

2. Activities and data collection

In the case of the Spanish pilot the main activity was concentrated at the “Colegio Vizcaya”, the school in Zamudio.

Firstly, with the aim of conducting a nutritionally and sustainable guideline that makes the most of the discards that are daily produced in a school canteen, **interviews** were carried out with the chef responsible from the canteen in order to get information about types of discards produced at the canteen, the way these discards are managed, the identified difficulties for discard management, and so on.

Moreover, taking into consideration the impact of these kinds of interventions at different societal levels, for instance, at school canteens, **a workshop on food waste valorization** was conducted in a school. Besides, a recipe-book was developed taking into consideration food waste generated at a school canteen.

The recipes will be available on the *Cook App*.

On the other hand, as a result of an analysis that was conducted about the main discards that are generated in the households, a **survey** was prepared for those families participating the discard management workshop, to evaluate the usefulness of the generated guideline.

Finally, a methodological video was developed to guide professionals on how an intervention to improve dietary habits should be conducted when its main goal is to measure the impact of the intervention on behavioural change and health parameters. The video will be available on the e-learning platform.

A detailed information about how CS9 has been developed in the Spanish pilot can be found in annex 3.2.

3. Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for the CS9 Spanish pilot.

4. The following indicators are set to monitor the progress of CS9 in the Spanish pilot.

- Outputs generated:
 - A nutritional and culinary guideline with 14 new recipes for discard management in households.
 - A gastronomic guideline with 10 new recipes for discard management in school canteens.
 - A methodological video about the methods to be applied when analysing the impact of dietary habits modification on health parameters.
- Number of participants in the survey - expected at least 60 results from a survey about the use of recommended recipes in households.

DANISH PILOT

1. Recruitment of participants

In the case of the Danish pilot CS9 target audience are mainly canteen's users and staff. In this sense, several recruitment methods are being used, for example social networks such as Facebook, LinkedIn or Instagram, brochures, and private and customer mail list invitations.

To reach a wider audience with dissemination purpose, other channels, such as participation in events, for example the Zamudio fair, are also considered.

2. Activities and data collection

The methodology followed in the Danish pilot includes different kind of methods and activities, a survey to collect information, training sessions with target audience (students and staff of the canteens) and awareness-raising activities, for example:

- Lectures and Discussion on zero waste cooking, future diets and "Planet in Balance".
- Plant-based zero waste cooking workshops with users of the canteens.
- Zero waste cooking school events at JTK main kitchen.
- Plant-based cooking schools at JTK main kitchen.
- Food choice motives and food waste behaviour survey.

All the activities are being reported through the SAM.

3. Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for the CS9 Danish pilot.

The following indicators are set to monitor the progress of CS9 in the Danish pilot.

- Number of Workshops organized- Two workshops per year with at least 30 participants.
- Number of participants in the behaviour survey - expected 400 respondents to the knowledge-attitude-behaviour survey.

SLOVAK PILOT

1. Recruitment of participants

In the case of the Slovak pilot, CS9 follows the methodology of the Spanish pilot. In this sense, they will focus on a School in Slovakia. To that aim they will direct contact directly with the school managers. Other participants in the CS9, such as the school canteens, or the families, will be recruited by the school managers.

As they aim to reach a wider audience, other recruitment methods such as open calls, social media or participation in conferences or dissemination events are also considered.

2. Activities and data collection

The methodology in the Slovak pilot for CS9 is a compilation of different methods for:

- information gathering,
- training and

- dissemination activities to increase knowledge and raise awareness among the target groups.

The methodology followed in the Spanish pilot will be also adapted to carry out the activities at the school in Slovakia.

Some of the methods to be applied:

- Surveys, interviews and workshops will be deployed for information gathering.
- Presentations and discussions - workshops for women with the aim to increase their skills and spread the information regarding healthy and sustainable diets –with practical examples will be performed.
- Replication of the Spanish model of the CS9 to be done in cooperation with Pilot school and parents of children. The school will be chosen through a self-assessment, afterwards surveys, workshops and guidance will be used to implement our methodologies and e-learning materials.
- Dissemination activities to increase awareness and promote healthier habits such as taking part in various conferences on the topic of FLW in Slovakia.

3. Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for the CS9 Slovak pilot.

The following indicators are suggested to monitor the progress of CS9 in the Slovak pilot.

- Number of participants at events - *at least 200 people.*
- Number of respondents to surveys and interviews - *at least 200 people.*
- Number of gathered recipes/tips on FW other data - *at least 25 recipes.*
- Measuring the impact from using methodologies/various tools in the population/school sample.
- Evaluating formulas to be sent to participants/attendees – *Average value of satisfaction over 8 in a 10 points scale for the participants of the CS.*

3.9.5. Schedule of the CS development

The activities listed below have either been completed or are scheduled. As said before, the activities are being reported at the SAM and this a sample of the implementations being carried out in the context of CS9 in each pilot.

Spanish pilot

- May 2022: Workshop and nutritional and the culinary guideline for families.
- October 2022: The culinary guideline for school canteens.
- December 2022: The methodological video.

Danish pilot

- October 26th, 2021: February 2nd, 2022; March 2022: Zero waste cooking activities.
- March 2022; December 2022: Reduce your CO2 activities.
- Ongoing: Green day (only vegetarian dishes at the canteens), green Tuesday, green Thursday.

- March 2022: Future days (dissemination activity).
- September 2022: Aarhus Food Festival (dissemination activity).

Slovak pilot

- February 2022 to May 2022: Surveys conducted to gather tips and recipes regarding FW from the public, other regions, ethnologists, and cooks.
- July 2022: Preparation of materials for the e-learning and ZW e-book.
- Fall 2021, 2022 and 2023: Zero waste brunch.
- April 2022: Attendance at the Really Healthy school conference.
- Spring 2023: Pilot school dissemination of nutritionally balanced and sustainable guidelines and other prepared methodologies, tracking progress.
- May 2022: Attendance at the conference *Degustorium* with ZW and FW focus group workshops and activities for children.
- Spring 2023: Intervention at schools following the Spanish pilot's methodology.
- Other activities to be deployed later in the project.

3.10. CS10. Working groups to discuss innovative models with entrepreneurs (social and non-social) to develop new business as well as exosystemic alliances among stakeholders and volunteer agreements signature.

This section describes the methodology for developing CS10.

3.10.1. Objective

Identify new business models as well as exosystemic alliances among stakeholders and promote the signing of voluntary agreements.

This CS is developed in the context of the 8 workshops hosted by work package 4 (WP4) and further information will be found in D4.1. The CS is developed jointly by all pilots.

3.10.2. Expected result

New business models derived from the activity.

3.10.3. Stakeholder mapping - Participants in the development of the CS10

In the development of CS10 experts, social actors' representatives, experienced social innovative companies' start-ups and supermarkets will be involved in addition to FOODRUS partners. Table 12 summarizes the stakeholder's profiles to participate in this CS.

Table 12: Description of the Stakeholders and their roles in CS10 for each pilot.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	ROLE
Pilot Leaders	Recruitment of participants. Design and development of activities. Data collection and Analysis.
Stakeholders of each pilot	Participate in the activities, data providers and testers.
Social actors	Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers and testers.
Start-ups	Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers and testers.
Companies	Participate in the activities as knowledge and data providers and testers.

3.10.4. Methodology

1. Recruitment of participants

Potential participants will be recruited by direct invitations to participate in the study. In this sense, once the target organizations have been identified, emails and phone calls will be performed to encourage organizations' participation. The recruitment process will be carried out by the pilot leaders.

Some of the stakeholder's profiles aimed to participate in this activity for example in the Spanish pilot are: experts, social actors' representatives, experienced social innovative companies (as *Koopera*⁷, integrated social services related to the topic or not), start-ups...

2. Activities and data collection

For a successful implementation of the CS10 two types of approaches can be adopted:

- Create **working groups** with participants to discuss successful cases, identify new models and reflect on the models themselves, social canvas, market analysis to foster the offer and demand, identify gaps.
- **Open innovation challenges** and marathons.

While working groups are limited to a smaller number of people and allow for in-depth discussions, open challenges and marathons give access to a larger number of stakeholders and ideas. In this sense, both methods can be combined.

The Slovak pilot has the intention to create an Alliance of Supermarkets as a platform for sharing the best practices in the area of prevention and reduction of FLW.

The Danish will organize eight workshops (D4.1) on the topic of food waste hierarchy and circular economy solutions, hosted in collaboration with ARC+, UD and AIN.

WP4 and WP6 are the WPs supporting pilots in the development of business expansion models. Once these have been approved by the coordinator they will be described and analysed further in WP4

⁷ <https://www.koopera.org/>

3. Planned Key Indicator performance (KPI) and Objectives for the CS10 Spanish pilot.

- Number of people participating in the 8 WP workshops - minimum 500 in total.
- Number of entities represented in the activity and types. At least 10 entities.
- Number of ideas identified to reduce food waste. At least 6 ideas.

3.10.5. Schedule of the CS development

To be determined by each pilot coordinator or activity responsible.

4. CONCLUSION

The objective of this document is to provide the pilots with a methodology that allows them to implement the CS activities. In this sense, this document describes the methodology for implementing the 10 citizen science activities. To that aim, first, a description of citizen science-based methods and their advantages and barriers to be applied in research projects has been provided in section 1. Then a methodology to introduce citizen science in the research projects is described in section 2. In this sense the main aspects to be taken into account are described, and a template to help with the designing of citizen activities has been proposed in table 2.

This general approach has been used to propose a methodology for each of the citizen science activities to be developed in this project. Moreover, the specificities of each pilot are considered, as there is no one-size-fits all CS method and contextual factors influence how CS are being implemented in each region.

The implementation of the CS will take place in the context of several WPs, in this sense the details and the results will be explained mainly in D1.4 and D4.1.

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6. ANNEX 1 – Narrative production materials

6.1. Script for the narrative production used in CS3 for the Spanish and Slovak Pilot.

1. Introduction:

- *Name, age, place of birth, number of children and grandchildren, profession, number of persons living in the household.*

2. Perception of waste:

- *What is your view on food wastage today?*
- *What is wasted most of all, and why?*

3. Looking back:

- *If we look back, how has it changed? How was food used in the past?*
- *What memories do you have from your childhood? Who was in charge of using food? What was the role of the community?*
- *Who taught you how to use food? How was this passed on? What about now?*
- *What things were not thrown away and eaten before but are not now?*

4. CHANGES AND CAUSES:

- *What changes have there been in food habits?*
- *(Changes in lifestyles) Why do we have less time?*
- *What influences today's wastefulness, what habits have changed?*
- *What influence does consumerism have in all this?*

5. FOOD SHOPPING HABITS:

- *How do you plan your shopping? How often do you shop? Where?*
- *How do you prepare food at home?*
- *how do you organise it, food for the whole week,*
- *Every day? Do you prepare food for more people (sons, grandchildren...)?*
- *Do you buy in bulk?*
- *Do you know where the food comes from? Do you usually look at the labels of the products, what do you look for?*
- *Do you buy seasonal products? On sale? Promotions?*
- *Do you take your trolley? Bags from home?*
- *Do you usually consider the best-before date?*
- *What do you do to know that a food is wrong?*

6. ON THE USE OF PLASTIC:

- *How much plastic do you use? Do you know about alternatives to plastic use? Do you put them into practice? why not?*

7. WASTE:

- *How do you distribute/separate your rubbish?*
- *Who throws the rubbish away? How often? Where? What type of bin do you use most?*
- *Who prepares the bags, who recycles?*
- *What do you do with batteries and oil? And with the used electrical appliances?*

8. PROPOSALS:

- *What do you think could be the 3 main lines of action against waste in your town, village and/or neighbourhood?*
- *What local initiatives could be put in place? And from your association?*

6.2. Methodology used in CS9 for the Spanish Pilot.

1. Stakeholders' engagement and information gathering.

Hold the first meetings with the general manager of the school (Colegio Vizcaya in the case of the Spanish pilot) and the chef responsible of the school canteen (Zamudio, Vizcaya). 29th October 2021

A first meeting was organised to discuss the interest of the school and the families to participate in the activity. Moreover, several other meetings were conducted with chefs from the school canteen to obtain information regarding the food waste generated at the canteen and to co-create recipes to increase the valorisation of their food waste.

2. Development of a guideline on healthy and sustainable dietary recommendations, together with recipes to promote food valorization at households. Delivered in May 2022.

The guideline was developed to be delivered during the workshop that was conducted at Colegio Vizcaya the 26th, May 2022.

3. Development of a recipe-book on food valorization at school canteens, *Finished by September 2022*

The recipe-book is being developed and will be finished by the end of October 2022.

4. Organize a workshop on FW valorization to show people the potential culinary value of FW.

The workshop was conducted at the school. 26th May 2022.

5. Analyze the impact of the training activities.

A survey for the families from the school was prepared.

- To develop a survey to be completed BEFORE delivering a workshop about sustainable diets. Workshop conducted on May 26th, 2022.
- Survey to be completed 1 month AFTER delivering the workshop about sustainable diet. Survey completed by 30th June 2022

7. ANNEX 2 – Reviewers' tables

Deliverable: 2.3 (M18)

Name: Zuzana Madajová

Email: zousca@gmail.com

Partner: Free Food

	Yes	No	Score 1-5 (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		4	Please correct formatting of the Content and wherever dates / chronology is mentioned pls make sure it has the same formatting
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		4	The document is still a working file and its final version shall be submitted in M28
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	The document is still a working file and its final version shall be submitted in M28
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		4	There are some inconsistencies throughout different pilots' inputs
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		4	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		3	Some references see it be missing
Glossary present in the document?		X	NA	

Reviewer n° 1

Date: 15.05.2022

Deliverable: D2.3**Name: Anetta Vaculíková****Email: aneta.orusi@gmail.com****Partner: NEDU**

	Yes	No	Score 1-5 (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	After the review and some amendments that were made according to the suggestions, the document has a clear structure now and I find the content as well as technical description, language and overall format very well performed.
Glossary present in the document?	X		5	

Reviewer n° Anetta Vaculíková NEDU**Date: 14.05.2022**

Deliverable: 2.3 (M28)**Name: Zuzana Madajová****Email: zousca@gmail.com****Partner: Free Food**

	Yes	No	Score 1-5 (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		4	Please correct formatting as per Comments
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		4	The document lays out the methods used to perform Citizen Science Activities by the different pilots in a clear and structured way
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	The document follows clear structure which is well developed for each CS and the pilot throughout the document
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		4	please see the Comments
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	The document is mainly focused on describing different CS methodologies. These are in fact a partial result of the activities involving citizens directly participating in their creation.
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		4	please see some suggestions in the Comments
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		4	see the comments
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	
Glossary present in the document?		X	NA	

Reviewer nº 1**Date: 27.02.2023**

Deliverable: 2.3 (M28)**Name: Anetta Vaculikova****Email: aneta.orusi@gmail.com****Partner: NEDU**

	Yes	No	Score 1-5 (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		4	Please correct formatting as per Comments
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	The document lays out the methods used to perform Citizen Science Activities by the different pilots in a clear and structured way
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	The document follows clear structure which is well developed for each CS and the pilot throughout the document
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		4	more details in comments
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	The document is mainly focused on describing stages of different CS methodologies and their progress.
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		4	please see some comments and suggestions
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	
Glossary present in the document?		X	NA	

Reviewer n° 2**Date: 27.02.2023**